

Short name	Cultural factors	Long name	Common cultural denominators affect all stakeholders
Geographical scope	National level		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	Common cultural denominators ¹ affect all stakeholders (i.e. laypeople and experts) and shape their risk perceptions in one society similarly. Each society has its very own understanding that decides what is of concern, how to deal with the risk, and what should be given higher priority		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	Utilising the overlooked impact of common cultural denominators when dealing with the risks and uncertainties of CC(U)S is crucial for risk governance of CCUS projects vis-à-vis social acceptance. It is likely that country-specific attitudes influence CC(U)S acceptance (e.g. Germany vs. Sweden).		
Other issues this affects	Common cultural denominators affect other important factors like trust in stakeholders in societies		
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Karimi, F. (2021). Stakeholders' risk perceptions of decarbonised energy system: Insights into patterns of behaviour. <i>Energies</i>, 14(21), 7205. • Karimi, F., & Toikka, A. (2018). General public reactions to carbon capture and storage: Does culture matter?. <i>International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control</i>, 70, 193-201. 		

¹ Common cultural denominators is 'the collective programming of the mind', such as shared societal values which distinguishes the members of one society from another.